

SYNTACTIC CONSTRUCTION OF ADVERTISING TEXTS

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada hozirgi zamon o'zbek tili tizimida faol jarayonlarni aks ettiruvchi reklama matnining sintaktik xususiyatlariga bag'ishlanadi. Tashqi, internet, TV reklama matnlari tahlilga tortiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: reklama matni, grammatik, leksik birliklar, stilistik vositalar, sintaktik konstruktsiya, sodda gap, qo'shma gap.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена изучению синтаксических особенностей рекламного текста, отражающего активные процессы в системе современного узбекского языка. В статье анализируются тексты внешней, интернет- и телевизионной рекламы.

Ключевые слова: рекламный текст, грамматика, лексические единицы, стилистические средства, синтаксическая конструкция, простое предложение, сложносочиненное предложение.

Abstract. The article is devoted to studying the syntactic features of the advertising text, which reflects the active processes in the modern Uzbek language system. The paper analyzes external, internet, and TV advertising texts.

Keywords: advertising text, grammatical, lexical units, stylistic means, syntactic construction, simple sentence, compound sentence

Currently, advertising has penetrated almost all areas of our lives. Despite the fact that the concept of advertising plays an important role in society and is widely used in everyday life, it is considered as one of the controversial topics in modern scientific literature. In addition, the concept of advertising is analyzed from different points of view, and each approach is diverse due to its diversity.

If the criterion of historical chronology is used, then it is shown that this is one of the forms of communication, as the first part of advertising. It is initially aimed at forming interpersonal relations between participants in market relations in the process of selling products. Ancient traders formed these connections literally with the spoken word. Outlets were billed as high-profile and repeat reviews of sellers. Therefore, it is no coincidence that the word "advertising" comes from the Latin word "reclamo," that is, "bayrkok," "cyrmak," "buymak." In this context, we can agree that the etymology of the word "Advertising" is related to the fact that the main function of etymology is information (information transmission) on oral social data channels, and the advertising board is carried out by the product owner, aimed at certain purposes, focused on a certain circle of people (target audience). This approach to understanding advertising is supported by many other experts. For example, the American Marketing Association (AMA) describes this as follows:

"Advertising is any paid form of providing and promoting products, ideas, or services without an identity on behalf of a known sponsor" [1; 98].

English advertising specialist F. Defkins refers to the description of the British Institute of Advertising Practice: "Advertising is the most reliable and affordable way to inform future consumers about a specific product or service" [2; 45]. As you can see, he also considers advertising a form of communication.

Advertising is a modern way of advertising goods and services. Currently, advertising is successfully developing and improving.

Suggestions of the advertising text are determined depending on the scope of its use. This factor has a particular impact on the type of print advertising. To achieve its goals, advertising text is forced to make the most of language tools. In a sense, the advertising message is a kind of concentration of language means: minimal words are used and maximum information is provided.

The pragmatic direction of advertising text requires the choice of grammatical, lexical units, stylistic tools, special syntax, printed materials and elements of various sign systems.

The basic unit of syntax is a sentence. The main tool of formation, explanation and expression of opinion is a syntactic unit formed on the basis of the laws and rules of a certain language. The main functional feature of speech is communicativity, that is the task of expression and explanation. Language is the most important mean of expressing opinion among people, and therefore it is the main tool that creates this function of language. Neither word nor phrase can perform this task. Their task is to name things and events, signs, actions, that is, a nominative problem [3; 22].

The creation of text advertising at the syntactic level is aimed at attracting the attention of the consumer and maintaining his interest. In addition, for the successful realization of the main advertising goal, that is, the sale of goods, there are certain models for organizing information in the advertising texts, and for its successful implementation, topics in the advertising text play an important role.

Simple sentences with two basic parts can be called a unique source of expression and semantic completeness of speech, since they have complete information on both the topic and the movement button. Such sentences have a special meaning, and their understanding always has one meaning.

In the same sentences, predicativity is expressed by one head and denotes an object (name) or movement (person specific, person indefinite, mismanagement) and thereby focuses on them. In these syntactic units there is always a text under the text, a hidden meaning, thanks to which these units will have the power of psychological influence on a person.

Unlike simple words, advertising texts use little. This is laconism of speech in Uzbek ("Greek laconismos - brevity - brevity and clarity in the presentation of opinion"¹) is validated basing on the same concept. For example, Buy 100 m³ of concrete and get a three-hour free automotive concrete pump service! Drink Fanta, rejoice! advertising texts are examples of joint advertising which is rare in Uzbek. As you know, non-participation of subject in sentence in Uzbek language is normal. This is because morphological means (personality forms) indicating the noun have the ability to exist in predicate. In the above advertising texts, the

¹ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lakonizm>

available predicates (buy, own, drink, pay) also allowed the subject (in all cases words should have acted as subject) and thereby shorten the text. Only 20 percent of the volume of selected advertising texts are joint conversations, because 1) the cost of advertising in all periods and economic requirements require this; 2) during the development of social networks, the attention of users can be explained by a large number of attracting tools (joint conversations require long attention). It should be noted that most of the texts of advertising in the format of a joint conversation are complex joint statements (composed of three or more simple sentences). Get cards, shop, and collect bonuses in a single account! Korzinka.uz Advertising texts of this nature testify to our opinion.

Compound sentences play a special stylistic role in advertising texts and serve to increase their effectiveness and emotional scope. In advertising texts, coherent fragments perform an aesthetic function in addition to a spiritual function, they are a vivid example of a logical presentation of the material and speech expression. "The same formation, the same answer to the same question, and the speaking with a counting tone"[4; 142] are considered important emotional tools in attracting attention in compound sentences. For example, Rengalin - for the treatment of dry and wet cough! As we know, "Estet" has doors suitable for any taste and design. The predicative parts in the advertising texts (dry and wet, taste and design) also enriched the content of the text (which types of cough are beneficial, what the doors are suitable for). It has also increased advertising effectiveness (the support of the adopted word for pragmatic purposes). 17 % of these sentences comprises compound parts. Most of the classified advertising materials are advertisements for the advertised goods (services) or their verification requirements (for example, medical advertisements). Compound constructions have a large semantic capacity and provide logical clarity when expressing an idea. It should be noted that the enumeration of cohesive clauses without a conjunction emphasizes the dynamism and tension of the situation, and multiple conjunctions help to create a smooth, melodious tone, thus making the enumeration more extensive and general. It is no coincidence that most of the parts of complex sentences are in the form of organized clauses (For example, advertisements texts like Play, dance, have fun with ORIO! Always play!).

The main task of the advertising text is to attract attention to a certain product, product, object or event through a relatively short message. The brevity and meaningfulness of noun phrases are suitable for this task, which leads to their frequent use in advertising texts. Such texts using noun phrases are found in contextual advertising. These advertising texts, despite their shortness, are very bright and memorable due to the placement of the product name in a separate sentence and unconventional graphic design.

In terms of the degree of use in advertising language, possessive sentences take the second place among one-part sentences after noun phrases. Non-possessive expressions are common in advertising language, which is constantly enriched with the facts of everyday language. The use of non-possessive constructions makes it possible to describe situations characterized by passivity, to give an action a certain lightness and, if necessary, to highlight the action itself or the situation without referring to any person.

Most syntactic constructions have unlimited figurative expression possibilities, which makes it possible to use them in creating effective advertising texts. For example, noun phrases are essentially created for description: by naming objects, decorating them with descriptions, advertisers describe everyday life, conditions, and evaluate the world around

them. In advertising texts, the name of the advertised thing (service) is given as a noun phrase. Adverb clauses are usually required to be interpreted by subsequent clauses. According to its communicative function, the noun phrase indicates the existence of the named object or event in the sentence. Adverbs are used to draw attention before this next comment. Attention is the most important thing for advertising texts. After all, "such statements indicate the existence of an object or event at the present moment, confirm the fact of this existence"[5; 135]. Advertising texts using adverbial sentences (the following sentences are meant) can be in the form of a compound sentence (Teze'lon.uz. Find it quickly, sell it quickly) or in the form of a simple sentence (Magne B6. Don't be too nervous). Verbal phrases make up 35% of the selected advertisements.

Speaking about the types of statements in advertising texts, we must not forget that different types of words, different syntactic constructions perform different stylistic functions in speech. In this sense, we can say that each syntactic tool in the analyzed advertising texts has its own task in realizing the advertising goal.

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